

POLICY BRIEF

No. 03, 2024

A Regional Overview of Gender Sensitive Dimensions in the European Agricultural Sector

Tamara Avellan^{1,2}, Nidhi Nagabhatla¹, Bishal Dahal², Amal Sarsour¹

Highlights

The following are 5 points that highlight the need to boost gender mainstreaming in the European agriculture process and policies. In this policy brief, we call for decision-makers and policy bookmakers to prioritise and integrate the unique perspectives from gender sensitivity into decision-making processes toward supporting sustainable production systems in the agriculture sector.

1. Underrepresentation of gender-sensitive practices and policies, particularly women's representation in European farm management, land ownership, and agricultural research, reflects a significant gap in current processes and policies at regional and national levels. Existing normative procedures do not adequately address the systemic barriers faced by women, often resulting in unequal opportunities and limited participation in decision-making.
2. Despite evidence showing that women have more significant consideration for holistic approaches to sustainable water management in agriculture, regional and state-level policy measures currently do not reflect this perspective.
3. In the context of 'buy-in' for the technology support system in the agricultural system, it is essential to note gender-disaggregated responses. Women are more inclined to adopt environmentally and socially friendly technologies, such as nature-based solutions. However, current policies do not adequately incentivise or support this technology uptake.
4. Efforts to increase gender representation in regional agricultural processes and value chains are being made at the European level. Still, these efforts must be strengthened and scaled up in a time-specific agenda. Policy measures could prioritise increasing female representation in all areas of the agriculture sector, including research, land ownership, and farm management.
5. The need for more gender-balanced European agricultural systems is still a significant barrier to the region's sustainable agricultural (food and water security) pathways. Policymakers need to take a more inclusive approach, including women and other underrepresented groups, in designing and implementing policies to ensure that policies meet the needs of all stakeholders and lead to more sustainable outcomes and resilient societies.

The policy brief has important implications for policy and practice in the agricultural sector and related aspects. We suggest that efforts to promote sustainable agriculture and water management consider gendered differences in perceptions and priorities in various sub-regions and states in the EU. Understanding these differences is crucial for promoting equitable, inclusive, and sustainable resource management and could involve targeted communication and capacity-building campaigns tailored for different gender groups. It could also include supporting processes toward greater representation of women in decision-making processes and ensuring their perspectives are meaningfully considered.

Background and Context

Gender representation in European agriculture and other sectoral agendas and policies is a complex issue that has received increasing attention recently (See Figure 1). While there have been efforts to promote gender equality, women

continue to be underrepresented in many areas of agricultural research and policy, such as decision-making, incentive processes, and training. Recently, a study commissioned by the European Parliament’s Committee on Women’s Rights and Gender Equality showed that women represent only around 30% of European agricultural researchers and are particularly underrepresented in leadership positions. These disparities include initiatives to promote gender mainstreaming and programmes to increase and increase balanced gender participation in various processes and programmes (European Parliament, May 2019).

The European Union’s gender equality targets and agenda for research and innovation, such as the European Standard on Gender Mainstreaming, aim to ensure that women are adequately represented in all areas of scientific research, including in the agricultural sector. While progress has been made in promoting gender equality, much work still needs to be done to ensure gender-equal access to resources, capacity, competencies, and decision-making roles. These critical aspects are noted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Gender mainstreaming policy process cycle adapted from the European Institute for Gender Equality and the European Standard on Gender Mainstreaming in the European Social Fund. Sources: (EIGE 2017/EU Parliament 2012; A/RES/64/292, UN 2010; A7-0235/2012)

The above-mentioned articles are from the European Parliament resolution of 11 September 2012 on the role of women in the green economy (2012/2035(INI))

In this policy brief, we also delve into the factors influencing the adoption of gender-sensitive approaches in the agricultural sector and advocate for the identification of gaps and the removal of barriers to implementing gender-sensitive strategies while providing an overview of gender dimensions within the European agricultural sector, highlighting that addressing challenges and opportunities for promoting gender equality and sustainability remains a critical component for EU's food security.

Gender has been a prominent focus in environmental discourse since the 1970s, shedding light on the distinct impact of environmental issues on men and women. Despite active female participation in ecological movements, their representation in governmental decision-making needs improvement (EIGE, 2017). Assessments by the Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI) across Europe show a lack of critical analysis and limited efforts to quantify the redistribution of direct payments and other Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) interventions across farm sizes and in terms of gender, age, and territories. This oversight has led to incomplete statements in legislative

settings, potentially diverting attention from these crucial issues (CAP, 2023).

The reformed CAP, effective from January 1, 2023, aims to establish a fairer, greener, and more performance-based agricultural policy. It seeks to support smaller farms, provide flexibility for EU countries to tailor measures to local conditions, and align with the ambitions of the European Green Deal, Farm to Fork, and biodiversity strategies (EU, 2023). Despite recognising the importance of women in the farming sector, their representation in leadership roles across EU member states remains inadequate, constituting only 29% of farm managers. Figure 2 (below) and Box 1 (next page - media discourse) reveal significant disparities between countries in the region. Key points are reflected in the regional trends: in France, women represent one-third of the agricultural workforce, with a steady increase in participation over the last decade. However, in Germany, women manage only around one in 10 farms, indicating a lag in gender parity within the agricultural sector. **Additionally, note that only one in five individuals set to inherit or take over farms is a woman.**

Figure 2. Women in agriculture across some selected EU countries adapted from EURACTIV article: [Agrifood Special Capitals Brief: Women in Agriculture](#)

As we contemplate the impact of existing regional and sub-regional socioeconomics and socio-cultural norms on gender groups within the agricultural sector, it becomes evident that understanding these dynamics is paramount for enhancing

the gender-specific implications of agricultural progress. Existing information reflects that gender evaluations play a crucial role in the agricultural sector, offering systematic and objective assessments of design, planning, implementation,

Box 1

Snapshots of gender-focused article from EURACTIV, mainly from reports by Sarantis Michalopoulos¹

Women in the Agrifood Industry How Cross-gender Collaboration Impacts a Successful Transformation of the Sector, Mar 31, 2023.

Discusses gender equality and its substantial meaning for innovation in the agri-food sector. Per European Commission regulations related to the industry, women and men are involved in agriculture worldwide, although their roles differ significantly by region and are changing rapidly.

“Gender equality is not a women’s issue; it is a human issue.”

<https://www.euractiv.com/section/agriculture-food/opinion/women-in-the-agrifood-industry-how-cross-gender-collaboration-impacts-a-successful-transformation-of-the-sector/>

“Women Bring Lousy Luck to Crops”: Fighting Stereotypes in Agriculture, Oct 16, 2019.

Spotlights the social-cultural norms in Portugal.

How #women’s “multifunctionality” can play in helping the sector advance, especially when it comes to reviving the declining rural areas in the EU and preventing further urbanisation

<https://www.euractiv.com/section/agriculture-food/news/women-bring-bad-luck-to-crops-fighting-stereotypes-in-agriculture/>

Is There Room for Women Farmers in the CAP? March 5, 2019

Discusses how women could be encouraged to join the sector. Moreover, what is the role of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)?

#Women have a key role in helping revive rural areas- discrimination against women in the farming sector is still widespread.

https://www.euractiv.com/section/agriculture-food/special_report/is-there-room-for-women-farmers-in-the-cap/

‘Multifunctional’ women could save EU rural areas, March 14, 2017.

Demonstrates advantages of women’s multifunctionality in boosting the potential of rural areas.

#A new approach should be adopted for the development of the rural areas, and EU member states and local authorities should provide rural people, especially women

<https://www.euractiv.com/section/agriculture-food/news/multifunctional-women-could-save-eus-rural-areas/>

Strengthening the strategic role of women in rural communities, Feb 8, 2017 (updated: Jan 23, 2018).

This reflects how the rural population in Spain empowers women in the agricultural sector.

#More and more women are finding empowerment through agriculture. In turn, they guarantee the survival of rural communities and the growth of the rural economy.

<https://www.euractiv.com/section/agriculture-food/video/strengthening-the-strategic-role-of-women-in-rural-communities/>

¹ Euractiv is an independent pan-European media network specialised in EU affairs, established by its Founder Christophe Leclercq in 1999. Sarantis Michalopoulos is a journalist and Senior Network Editor at Euractiv who writes extensively on EU Affairs with special regard to agriculture, food and health and follows closely the ongoing development of the European integration process. The box showcases selected snapshots of his gender-focused articles within the context of EU’s regional agriculture trends.

and results of activities, projects, programmes, or policies. Within the EU agriculture sector, focusing on gender impacts and promoting gender equality is crucial for enhancing gender sensitivity in the industry. The WATERAGRI (<https://wateragri.eu/>) project, with 23 partners from 12 European countries, underscores the necessity of explicitly addressing how gender-specific changes in the EU's agricultural sector can be promoted, especially within the countries implementing regional policies to foster gender equality and inclusivity in agriculture-focused value chains. This is a crucial point for future research initiatives to explore and tackle. While the project has examined how embracing a gender-sensitive approach can bolster sustainable production systems and resilience for individuals and communities involved in the agricultural sector at the EU level, particularly within the study area countries, broader regional considerations of gender-sensitive practices for sustainable agriculture are discussed within the context of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)

and related regulatory measures as noted in Box 2.

Regional Trends in Gender Representation in European Farm Management and Land Ownership

Gender inequalities persist in the agriculture sector in Europe, particularly in terms of farm management and land ownership. For instance, the extent of agricultural landholding by women varies across the region (European Union, hereafter, EU) depending on several social, economic, and cultural factors (Dixon, 1982). Per the European Commission report published by Eurostat, women are often significantly underrepresented in these areas, with only about 30% of farm managers being women. This gender disparity varies widely across countries, with some countries having higher rates of female farm managers, such as Latvia, Lithuania, and Estonia, where women constitute more than 40% of farm

Box 2

Key gender-focused points from Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and the Council (17 December 2013) on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Council Regulation (EC) [No 1698/2005](#)

Point 8 (page 2): Sub-programmes should concern, among others..., young farmers, small farms, mountain areas, the creation of short supply chains, women in rural areas, and climate change mitigation/adaptation/ biodiversity.

Point 17 (page 4): Diversification of farmers into non-agricultural activities and the setting up and development of non-agricultural SMEs in rural areas should be promoted. That measure should also encourage the entrepreneurship of women in rural areas.

Article 7 Thematic sub-programmes: Point 1 (page 15): To achieve the Union priorities for rural development, Member States may include thematic sub-programmes that address specific needs within their rural development programmes. The thematic sub-programmes may relate to (a) young farmers; (b) small farms as referred to in the third subparagraph of Article 19(2); (c) mountain areas as referred to in Article 32(2); (d) short supply chains; (e) women in rural areas; (f) climate change mitigation/adaptation /biodiversity.

Article 66 Managing Authority, Point 1 (page 44): reflects ensuring publicity for the programme, including through the national rural network, by informing potential beneficiaries, professional organisations, economic and social partners, bodies involved in promoting equality between men and women, and the non-governmental organisations concerned, including environmental organisations, of the possibilities offered by the programme and the rules for gaining access to funding as well as by informing beneficiaries of the Union contribution and the general public on the role played by the Union in the programme.

Annex IV Sub-Programmes in Article 7 (Page 58): mention 'in rural areas' in the context of knowledge transfer and information actions, advisory services, farm management, farm relief services, Investments in physical assets, and Farm and business development. Essential services and village renewal in rural areas, etc.

Figure 3. Overview of women farm managers in Europe; Source: Eurostat

managers. In countries like Finland, Germany, Denmark, and the Netherlands, women account for less than 15% of farm managers (Figure 3). It is crucial to note these gender gaps in the European agricultural landscape, and the lack of gender diversity in agriculture remains a challenge for sustainable development and pathways towards achieving gender equality in Europe.

Historical imbalances in land distribution and inheritance laws in this region and many parts of the world have systematically favoured men in agriculture, perpetuating a persistent gender gap in land ownership (Zhlhima et al., 2022). This inequality poses a significant barrier to women's economic empowerment, stemming from inadequate legal rights and insufficient cultural support for women to own and manage land. The issue is compounded by patriarchal norms and attitudes towards women's property rights, further restricting their access to land and impeding active participation in decision-making processes (Benschop, 2004).

Gender norms related to credit, education, and training significantly impact women's capacity to build land ownership and agricultural management skills. In various instances, women need help accessing financial resources, hindering their ability to invest in land and agricultural production. Addressing the gender gap requires targeted policies addressing disparities in tenure rights and training opportunities for women in agricultural management. Overcoming these challenges is crucial for fostering gender balance and ensuring women's equal participation and contribution to economic growth and development, particularly in agriculture (Ragasa et al., 2016). Existing information reflects that gender evaluations play a

crucial role in the agricultural sector, offering systematic and objective assessments of design, planning, implementation, and results of activities, projects, programmes, or policies. In the EU agriculture sector, the focus on gender impacts and the contribution to promoting gender equality are crucial to boosting gender sensitivity. A proactive approach towards conducting gender evaluations should not be confined to post-project assessments but should be integrated throughout project implementation. Continuous improvement evaluations are essential to ensure that gender equality considerations are woven into the fabric of agricultural initiatives. Per the synthesis by

GWP, adopting an ex-ante evaluation approach becomes instrumental in anticipating and mitigating potential gender disparities arising from agricultural policies and also aligns with the commitment to fostering gender equality in the water sector (<https://www.gwp.org/globalassets/global/activities/act-on-sdg6/advancing-towards-gender-maintreaming-in-wrm---report.pdf>).

Understanding Gender Representation in European Agricultural Research with Experiential Learning from the WATERAGRI Project

Our findings are rooted in the EU H2020 project WATERAGRI, intended to solve sustainable agricultural water management and soil fertilisation challenges to secure affordable food production in Europe for the 21st century (<https://wateragri.eu/>). This was implemented by developing a new framework for using small water retention approaches for managing excess and shortage of water and better recovery of nutrients from agricultural catchments applying a multi-actor approach. WATERAGRI aimed to develop these technologies in partnership with agricultural stakeholders to take up the developments as quickly as possible to address the impacts of climate change. Solutions were tested in fields in ten case studies across Europe. Each location came with a significant number of actors. The project applied a transdisciplinary approach of working with and through stakeholders in each site, allowing for learning experiences between consortium members and local actors (vertical learning) and learning experiences across actors of multiple locations (horizontal learning). See more in Box 3 (next page).

Box 3

The stakeholder composition reflects a predominantly male presence, constituting 83% of the stakeholders. Within this group, 36% identified as male researchers. Women stakeholders, representing 17% of the total, are mainly of Polish (6%), Hungarian (5%), or Finnish (6%) origin. Notably, 10% of the stakeholders are researchers, while 8% belong to advisory services. The register of consented stakeholders comprises nearly 127 individuals. The geographical distribution of consenting stakeholders is prominent in Italy (22), Hungary (20), Finland (17), and Poland (17). Additional contributors include Germany (10), Sweden (9), and France (8). Austria (5) and Switzerland (4) conclude the list. This analysis draws on existing information, shedding light on the gender and regional dynamics within WATERAGRI stakeholders, providing broad insights and aiming to inform strategic considerations and decision-making processes operating within the project's implementation phase.

The majority of stakeholders who provided consent are predominantly male (83%). Within this group, male researchers constitute the largest segment, comprising 36% of all stakeholders. When examining gender distribution across specific categories, such as researchers, decision-makers, and advisory services, the male-to-female ratio is approximately 3 to 1. Notably, within the farm category, the gender ratio is even more pronounced, with a ratio of 4 to 1. This data underscores a gender disparity in the operational aspects of project implementation, particularly in roles related to decision-making, advisory services, and on-farm activities.

In the realm of gender distribution across the region, a noteworthy observation emerges: most countries exhibit 50% or lower female participation rates.

Photos from the case site of the project:

Field preparations in the case study site in Sweden (top left) and Mistelbach, site visit in the case study in Austria (top right). Water quality analyses of the constructed wetland in the case study site in Italy (bottom left and bottom right). Photo (clockwise from top left): BOKU, BOKU, UNIBO, UNIBO.

Switzerland, Poland, Austria, and Finland stand out for their seemingly gender-balanced approach to project implementation strategy, with near-parity. However, it is imperative to contextualise Switzerland's statistics, given the overall low participation, rendering gender parity statistically inconclusive. Examining the gender distribution across regions reveals a prevalent trend where the majority exhibit 50% or lower female participation rates. Notably, Switzerland, Poland, Austria, and Finland stand out as countries adopting a somewhat gender-balanced approach to project implementation strategy, attaining a near equilibrium. In the case of Sweden and Germany, the composition of participants leans exclusively toward males, indicating some absence of female involvement. In Italy and Hungary, male participants predominantly influence the project teams, shaping the gender dynamics in these contexts. This analysis, conducted through a WATERAGRI lens, underscores the multifaceted nature of gender representation within the realm of project implementation strategy and calls for other projects funded by the EU to take on similar assessments as part of gender-sensitive exercise towards informing future commitments in this domain to apply a gender-sensitive approach.

The Delphi approach helped to define sustainability in the WATERAGRI H2020 Project, which involved 39 experts strategically selected using non-probabilistic and purposeful sampling techniques (Dahal et al. 2023). The selection criteria included expertise, relevance to the project, and substantial knowledge in the field. The experts represented the WATERAGRI consortium (9 from case study owners, 11 from solution providers), local stakeholders (10), and unrelated individuals (9). Careful consideration ensured diverse perspectives. The survey comprised 21 questions across various themes (One expert questioned the relevance of gender classification). The process involved distributing questionnaires to project team members and stakeholders, compiling responses, and analysing them. Results were presented to experts during the WATERAGRI General Assembly meetings every six months, allowing iterative refinement. Questions explored gender-sensitive sustainable water management, emphasising women's participation in decision-making, resource access, and integrating gender perspectives into research. This survey also provided a robust foundation for defining sustainability, aligning perspectives, and guiding effective strategies in water management policies and practices.

The self-assessment of knowledge of sustainable agricultural water management (SAWM) among experts revealed that female experts initially rated their SAWM knowledge as

neutral, reflecting a pattern of low participation in open-ended questions. The environmental pillar was consistently ranked as the most crucial in SAWM, with the majority emphasising its importance. Two experts highlighted the combined significance of the economic and environmental pillars, while one expert underscored the social pillar as the most important. Water availability and climate change emerged as primary concerns impacting gender groups.

In response to questions about sustainability and the environmental pillar, 8 of 9 experts emphasised water availability as the foremost concern in SAWM. Strategies mentioned included using irrigation water efficiently, reducing water loss/runoff, implementing precision irrigation systems, and optimising water use. Climate change was also a significant concern for 7 of 9 experts, who linked it to deforestation, extreme climatic events, and biodiversity loss. The alignment of responses with the prioritisation of the environmental pillar showcased a consistent pattern favouring ecological sustainability.

Stakeholder participation and co-decision-making surfaced as significant concerns in the social aspects of SAWM, with 5 out of 9 experts highlighting their importance. Recommendations included promoting inclusive governance, participatory decision-making processes, transparency, accountability, and support for water user associations and cooperatives. The emphasis on equal rights and a coordinated approach in participatory work was evident, with farmers and cooperatives identified as primary stakeholders, and some experts also mentioned government authorities.

Experts expressed concern about income and affordability in the economic pillar of sustainability, with 5 out of 9 highlighting it as a significant issue. The focus was upgrading farmers' economic status, enhancing financial capacity, and increasing income. Additionally, experts raised concerns about irrigation service fees and the affordability of low-cost technology affecting the cost of farm inputs.

Overall, the gender impact in the expert responses was not explicitly discussed in the provided text. However, the initial neutral self-assessment and the subsequent focus on environmental sustainability, stakeholder participation, co-decision-making, and economic concerns collectively underscore the need for a nuanced understanding of how these issues affect different gender groups. Further exploration into gender-specific perspectives and experiences within these pillars could provide deeper insights into the gendered implications of the Sustainable Agricultural Water

management approach.

While recent reforms in EU's policy on agriculture increasingly reflect gender-sensitive approaches, acknowledging the significant role of women in agricultural production and rural development efforts have been made to address gender disparities in access to resources, decision-making, and participation in agricultural activities. The operational deployment of these regulations needs to emphasise the importance of integrating gender perspectives into related policies, recognising that empowering women in agriculture is not only a matter of gender equality but also essential for sustainable and inclusive rural development. Understanding

the gender impact of interventions helps to understand the complex interplay between socio-technical systems, societal norms, and sustainability goals. One of the examples cited by Wolfram and Kienesberger (2023) is this one on gendered energy transition in Norway (Standal et al., 2022), which also looks at the barriers for the different genders to change to renewable energies, wherein women and men decide differently or equally for any of the solutions. In this context, we have outlined four key recommendations and overall guiding notes in Figures 4 and 5.

To advance gender equality in European agriculture, a multifaceted approach is essential. Advocacy efforts

Gender Specificity in Technology Uptake

Societal Dynamics

Gendering disrupts existing socio-technical systems, reinforcing their stability or challenging their entrenched norms in the broader social order.

Innovation and Sustainability

The gender lens shapes the disruptiveness and sustainability of innovations, influencing justice orientations and other sustainability propositions. The role of young generations becomes crucial in envisioning alternative futures.

Behavioral Shifts

The gender-sensitive approach encourages or discourages changes in daily practices and routines involving motives, meanings, competencies, and materials. This reflects a nuanced influence on individuals and communities.

Mediation in Transitions

Gender plays a mediating role in niche/regime interaction, influencing the amplification of emerging sustainability innovations. It can facilitate the imposition of mainstream solutions or promote the uptake of radical innovations.

Niche Zones

Gender considerations destabilize or stabilize niche formation. This involves social networking, self-organization, and the recognition of diversity, impacting the emergence of alternative practices.

Figure 4. Gender considerations in sustainable projects are pivotal in reshaping societal structures, influencing practices, and fostering innovation. A few crucial aspects shown in the figure are adapted from Wolfram and Kienesberger (2023).

must promote equal land ownership and management opportunities, recognizing women’s pivotal role in agroecology and agricultural practices and policies. To bridge gender gaps, a strategic focus on improving access to credit and education is crucial, with tailored initiatives addressing the specific gender needs of the sector. Additionally, implementing targeted measures such as funding schemes and training programs is imperative to foster gender-sensitive capacity building. To ensure effectiveness, interventions should be tailored to the diverse socio-economic and sociocultural systems prevalent at the state, national, and regional levels, acknowledging the nuanced challenges faced by men and women in different contexts. A gender-sensitive perspective in European agriculture mandates a comprehensive regional overview, acknowledging and addressing the unique dynamics

of each country/sub-region/settings to cultivate a more inclusive and equitable agricultural landscape.

From the analysis undertaken by the project we believe that the initiatives promoting gender sensitivity (access to land, finance, education, and technology and supporting women’s leadership and entrepreneurship) in the agricultural sector needs to be boosted and supported.

This policy brief reiterates that by prioritising gender equality in land ownership and promoting policies that support women’s economic empowerment, the EU can create more inclusive and sustainable agricultural systems that benefit all members of society and member states.

1. Addressing Cultural and Social Barriers	2. Understanding Gendered Perspectives in Sustainable Water Management	3. Promoting Environmentally and Socially Friendly Technology Uptake	4. Targeted Strategies to Address Gender Gaps
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tackle traditional gender roles /stereotypes hindering women’s economic empowerment. • Implement awareness-raising campaigns, mentoring programmes, and networks for female farmers. • Draw inspiration from existing EU policies, such as the Gender Action Plan for Rural Development and the European Charter for Rural Women, to promote women’s access to land, credit, education, and training. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognise that gendered differences in perceptions of sustainable water management may be rooted in socialization and gender roles. • Acknowledge that women, more affected by water scarcity, may prioritize water availability due to their greater responsibility for water management. • Highlight the need to address these gendered perspectives in policymaking noting cultural, social, economic, and environmental differences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritise the promotion of environmentally and socially friendly technology uptake, including nature-based solutions, in agricultural policies and programmes. • Recognise women’s greater inclination towards less labour-intensive solutions. • Develop a tailored gender strategy to promote equality in agriculture, aligning with regional governance strategies such as the Nature Restoration Laws and Water Directive. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement targeted strategies to increase gender participation in critical operational areas. • Advocate for inclusive policies that support women in decision-making roles. • Offer training programmes to contribute to a more equitable gender distribution in the project’s operational agenda. • Recognize and rectify gender disparities to foster a diverse and inclusive environment, ensuring a holistic and balanced approach to project implementation.

Figure 5. Key recommendation for EU stakeholders and policymakers linked to the agriculture sector

References

Benschop, M. (2004). "Women's Rights to Land and Property." Commission on Sustainable Development.

CAP. 2023. "A Fairer CAP"? | Analysing Fairwashing in CAP Talks and Practices. August 28, 2023. Matteo Metta. <https://www.arc2020.eu/a-fairer-cap-really>

Dahal, Bishal, Tamara Avellán, Ali Torabi Haghighi, and Bjørn Kløve. 2023. 'Defining Sustainability in Agricultural Water Management Using a Delphi Survey Technique.' *Water Policy* 25 (6): 597–621. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wp.2023.057>.

Dixon, R. B. (1982). "Women in Agriculture: Counting the Labor Force in Developing Countries." *Population and Development Review*, pp. 539–66.

EIGE. (2017). "Environment and climate change": Existing gender-equality policy objectives at EU and international level. <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/policy-areas/environment-and-climate-change>.

EU. 2023. The common agricultural policy: 2023-27. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-2023-27_en.

EURACTIVE. 2023. Agrifood Special Capitals Brief: Women in agriculture. <https://www.euractiv.com/section/agriculture-food/news/agrifood-special-capitals-brief-women-in-agriculture>

European Parliament. (2019). Report: The professional status of rural women in the EU. Policy Department for Citizens' Rights and Constitutional Affairs Directorate General for Internal Policies of the Union. EU, May 2019. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/608868/IPOL_STU\(2019\)608868_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/608868/IPOL_STU(2019)608868_EN.pdf)

Ragasa, Catherine, John Ulimwengu, Josee Randriamamonjy, and Thaddee Badibanga. 2016. "Factors Affecting Performance of Agricultural Extension: Evidence from Democratic Republic of Congo." *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension* 22 (2): 113–43.

Standal Karina et al. (2020). Engaging men and women in energy production in Norway and the United Kingdom: The significance of social practices and gender relations. *Energy Research & Social Science*, Volume 60, 2020, 101338, ISSN 2214-6296, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101338>.

Zhllima, Edvin, Dorina Pojani, Elvina Merkaj, and Drini Imami. 2022. "Unlabeled Class: Albania's Gender Gaps in Land Ownership and Inheritance." *Feminist Economics*, 1–32.

In partnership with:

A Regional Overview of Gender Sensitive Dimensions in the European Agricultural Sector

Copyright © United Nations University Institute on Comparative Regional Integration Studies, 2024

The views expressed in this publication are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the United Nations University.

Publisher: United Nations University Institute on Comparative Regional Integration Studies (UNU-CRIS), Bruges, Belgium

¹ UNU-CRIS, Bruges, Belgium

² University of Oulu, Oulu, Finland, tamara.avellan@oulu.fi

WATERAGRI (WATER RETENTION AND NUTRIENT RECYCLING IN SOILS AND STREAMS FOR IMPROVED AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION) is the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 858375 (<https://wateragri.eu/>)

Suggested citation: Avellan, Tamara., Nidhi Nagabhatla, Bishal Dahal, Amal Sarsour. 2024. A Regional Overview of Gender Sensitive Dimensions in the European Agricultural Sector. PB-2024-02. Bruges: UNU-CRIS